

DELIVERY OF PLEADINGS BY REMOTE MEANS FROM THE PRESPECTIVE OF THE RIGHT TO COURT

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Marcin DZIURDA¹

ABSTRACT. *As a rule, pleadings in civil proceedings in Poland are served in the paper form. There are only few types of proceedings (registry proceedings, bankruptcy proceedings, restructuring proceedings and electronic writ-of-payment proceedings) in which pleadings may be submitted in the electronic form using the ICT system made available by the court.*

An episodic regulation was implemented during the Covid-19 epidemic, whereby letters originating from the court (rulings, orders and notices) are delivered to advocates and attorneys-at-law by remote means of communication (court information portal). This regulation does not, however, apply to pleadings (originating from the parties) which continue to be delivered in the paper form.

It would be advisable to implement a duty, whereby pleadings are to be submitted in the electronic form which would make it possible to deliver them to the other party in the same form. However, it could only apply to parties who have professional legal representatives. Some participants of the court proceedings are still digitally excluded, and therefore, imposing the duty to submit pleadings in the electronic form on parties acting without a professional legal representative would violate their right to the court.

Keywords: *Right to the court, pleadings, service by remote means, ICT teleinformation system, information portal*

I. Legal status to date

The informatisation level of Polish civil proceedings is still very low [3, p. 349 *et seq*]. This comment applies in particular to the submission and service of pleadings (procedural documents). As a rule, those documents must be submitted and served in the written form. Even the Polish name “pismo procesowe”, which is literally translated as “a procedural document on paper”, implies that.

In accordance with Article 125 § 1 of the CPC², pleadings contain petitions and statements of the parties made outside the hearing. According to Article 125 §2 of the CPC, if a specific provision so requires, pleadings are to be submitted on official (template) forms, but still in paper. However, the number of proceedings in which such forms are applicable keeps getting lower. This is due to the fact that the official forms have not been well drafted in the first place, and rather than make the procedure easier, they made it more difficult. For that reason, as of 7 July 2019,³ mandatory forms were abandoned in simplified proceedings cove-

¹ Marcin DZIURDA, Assistant Professor at Chair of Civil Procedure, Faculty of Law and Administration, ORCID nr: 0000-0003-2896-818X, University of Warsaw, Poland

² Civil Procedure Code Act of 17 November 1964 (Polish Journal of Laws [Dz.U.] of 2021, item 1805 as amended).

³ In the Criminal Procedure Code’s and Certain Other Acts’ Amendment Act of 4 July 2019 (Polish

ring small claims up to PLN 20,000 (or, approx. EUR 4,200). Official forms are currently used in few proceedings, such as proceedings for an entry to the land and mortgage register.

According to Article 125 §2(1) of the CPC, if a special provision so requires, pleadings are to be filed only via the ICT teleinformation system. It is a special ICT system made available by the court which parties and representatives use for uploading pleadings with enclosures in the electronic form. At present, there are few types of proceedings in Poland that have been fully computerised – registry proceedings (Article 694(2a) of the CPC), and also bankruptcy proceedings¹ and restructuring proceedings².

The electronic writ-of-payment proceedings are partly computerised – these proceedings are used for a faster and cheaper³ enforcement of mass claims, e.g. by Internet providers against clients who don't pay their monthly bills. Using the electronic writ-of-payment proceedings is voluntary. However, if the claimant decides to take advantage of those proceedings, then pursuant to Article 505(31) § 1 of the CPC the claimant will submit pleadings only via the ICT system made available by the court⁴. The defendant, on the other hand, has a choice – pursuant to Article 505(31) § 2 of the CPC, the defendant may choose the ICT system or may submit pleadings in the traditional paper form.

As for other proceedings, and thus the majority of civil cases, the parties are still forced to submit pleadings in the paper form. They may be submitted directly in the court (in the court's registry office) or they may be posted in a post office. In accordance with Article 165 §2 1 of the CPC, posting of a pleading at a post office of the postal services operator (currently, it can be any postal operator⁵) within the meaning of the Polish Postal Law or at an outlet of an entity that delivers mail in the European Union is equivalent to lodging that pleading at the court.

Journal of Laws [Dz.U.], item 1469 as amended).

¹ Cf. Article 216a of the Bankruptcy Law Act of 28 February 2003 (Polish Journal of Laws [Dz.U.] of 2022, item 1520).

² Cf. Article 196a of the Restructuring Law Act of 15 May 2015 (Polish Journal of Laws [Dz.U.] of 2022, item 2309).

³ Pursuant to Article 19.2.2 of the Court Fees in Civil Cases Act of 28 July 2005 (Polish Journal of Laws [Dz.U.] of 2022, item 1125) only one fourth of the regular fee on the statement of claim is charged in the writ-of-payment proceedings.

⁴ All cases in the electronic writ-of-payment proceedings are heard by one court. It is the District Court for Lublin-West.

⁵ The regulation in Article 165 § 2 of the CPC was amended on 24 September 2021 as a result of the Court of Justice of the European Union judgement of 27 March 2019, Case C-545/17, Pawlak (ECLI:EU:C:2019:260). In the judgement, the CJEU decided that the first sentence of Article 7(1) of Directive 97/67/EC, as amended by Directive 2008/6/EC, read in conjunction with Article 8 of that directive, must be interpreted as precluding a rule of national law which recognizes only the posting of a procedural document at a post office of the sole operator designated to provide the universal postal service as being equivalent to lodging such a document before the relevant court. Such a limitation resulted from Article 165 § 2 of the CPC effective before 24 September 2021.

In Article 125 §2(1a) of the CPC, it was declared that it is possible to choose to submit pleadings via the ICT system and continue to submit pleadings via that system if it is possible for technical reasons on the part of the court. However, that regulation is empty. Apart from the above mentioned few types of proceedings, courts do not have technical capabilities to enable parties to submit pleadings via the ICT system. The Supreme Court does not have such capabilities at all; as a result, even in cases where pleadings during the proceedings before the common courts of law (of first- and second instance) are submitted in the electronic form, the pleadings are submitted only in paper when the cases are heard by the Supreme Court. According to Article 694(3a) § 1 of the CPC, where a petition in the proceedings before the registry court was submitted via the ICT system, all pleadings in that case are to be filed only via that system, except for remedies the review of which is within the remit of the Supreme Court.

Where pleadings are submitted in the paper form, their copies must be delivered to the parties in the same form¹. Official service is still the primary form of serving pleadings in Poland. As part of the official service, a party files a pleading with the court along with a copy and the court serves that copy in paper on the opposite party. As a rule, the court serves it by mail (Article 130 § 1 of the CPC). The postal operator responsible for the service is selected by way of a public procurement procedure.

The exception arises from Article 132 of the CPC. Under that provision, where both parties are represented by professional legal representatives (advocates, attorneys-at-law, patent attorneys and the General Counsel of the Republic of Poland), the professional legal representatives deliver the copies of pleadings to one another directly, without involving the court. It does not, however, include the statement of claim and the other most important pleadings, primarily the remedies². Usually, the delivering under Article 132 of the CPC is performing in the paper form. With these reservations in mind, in keeping with Article 132 § 1(3) of the CPC, professional representatives may choose delivering pleadings and enclosures to one another only in the electronic form if they submit a relevant joint statement to that effect to the court and provide the court with the contact details used for that purpose, particularly the e-mail address or the fax number. However, professional representatives rarely take advantage of that regulation. Firstly, the legislator unnecessarily included a reservation in Article 132 § 1(3) *in*

¹ Theoretically, according to Article 131(1) of the CPC, the courts serves the documents via the ICT system (electronic service) if the addressee lodged the pleading via the ICT system or if the addressee chose to submit pleadings via the ICT system. However, as previously mentioned, it is currently possible only in few types of proceedings – registry proceedings, bankruptcy proceedings and restructuring proceedings, and also, partly, electronic writ-of-payment proceedings.

² Direct service of the statement of claim and remedies is excluded because the court must go through them to find out whether or not they are correct in formal terms and whether or not the proper fees have been paid before they may be delivered to the other party.

fine of the CPC, whereby the statement on the choice of electronic service may not be revoked. Secondly, even if professional representatives do decide to submit pleadings in the electronic form to one another, they will still be required to submit a paper copy for the court (in practice, they will need to post it).

II. Episodic regulations during Covid-19 epidemic

After the Covid-19 pandemic outbreak, the Polish government implemented the Special Solutions to Prevent, Counteract and Combat Covid-19, Other Infectious Diseases and the Ensuing Crisis Situations Act of 2 March 2020¹(the Covid-19 Act). Among other things, it implemented changes to the civil proceedings [4, p.157]. In particular, it excluded collegiality of decision-making in common courts (Article 15 zzs(1) Section 1.4 of the Covid-19 Act), however collegiality of decision-making in the Supreme Court has not been excluded [7, p. 59]. Simultaneously, it significantly limited the openness of the proceedings (Article 15 zzs(1) Section 1.3 of the Covid-19 Act) [6, p. 4; 1, p. 125]. It is particularly controversial that, even though the restrictions are to be episodic, they will apply for one year following the end of the state of epidemic threat. Meanwhile, it wasn't until 16 May 2022 that the state of epidemic [*stan epidemii*] was changed to the state of the epidemic threat [*stan zagrożenia epidemicznego*]. It does not seem likely that the state of the epidemic threat will be recalled any time soon.

No regulations were implemented during the early stage of the Covid-19 epidemic that would expand the scope of cases in which pleadings may be submitted in the electronic form. Submitting pleadings in the electronic form was only possible in the few previously described types of proceedings where a special court ICT system is made available.

It was only when the epidemic situation stabilised, notably on 3 July 2021, that Article 15 zzs(9) of the Covid-19 Act was implemented². According to that provision, during the state of epidemic or the state of the epidemic threat announced because of Covid-19 and for one year from the recall of the latter, in the absence of the possibility of using the ICT system servicing the court proceedings (that is, in the absolute majority of cases), the court will serve pleadings on the advocate, attorney-at-law, patent attorney or the General Counsel of the Republic of Poland by posting them in the special ICT system used for making those pleadings available (the information portal).

This is how a new method of pleading service was implemented. However, that method is limited – pleadings posted in the information portal may only be

¹ *Ustawa z 2 marca 2020 r. o szczególnych rozwiązaniach związanych z zapobieganiem, przeciwdziałaniem i zwalczaniem Covid-19, innych chorób zakaźnych oraz wywołanych nimi sytuacji kryzysowych*, Polish Journal of Laws [Dz.U.] of 2021, item 2095 as amended.

² Pursuant to Polish Criminal Procedure Code's and Certain Other Acts' Amendment Act of 28 May 2021 (Journal of Laws, item 1090).

delivered to professional legal representatives. Thus, such a form of service cannot be applicable to parties who act in the court proceedings¹ in person.

Posting a pleading in the portal has the effect of its service on a professional representative. There are, however, concerns caused by the fact that, when implementing Article 15z(9) of the Covid-19 Act, which reads that pleadings are served on professional representatives via the information portal, the legislator did not impose a duty on advocates and attorneys-at-law to set up accounts on that portal. Thus, there are concerns whether or not posting a pleading in the portal has the effect of service (delivery) when the addressee (the advocate or attorney-at-law) did not set up an account on the portal [5, p. 223].

The greatest restriction on service of pleadings via the information portal is related to the fact that it can only be used for the service of court letters, that is on letters originating from the court. Those are primarily rulings (judgements and decisions), orders and notices (for example, notice of a hearing date). The portal may not, however, be used for the service of pleadings, that is letters originating from the parties. Those are still to be submitted in the paper form.

During the legislative works there was a proposal that the court should deliver pleadings of the opponent to the professional legal representatives by posting their scanned images on the portal². However, there was no will to combine that proposal with imposing a duty on the parties (or at least on the parties represented by professional legal representatives) to submit pleadings in the electronic form to the court. Had the solution proposed by the legislator been implemented, the burden of scanning the paper pleadings submitted by the parties would have been shifted to the court. It would be difficult for the courts to cope with in organisational terms. Thus, eventually, the catalogue of documents posted on the information portal was limited to documents originating from the court while excluding pleadings submitted by the parties.

III. Evaluation of electronic service from the perspective of procedural guarantees

Initially, there were concerns about the functioning of the information portal. They were even greater in view of the fact that the operating principles of that specific ICT system used for giving access to court letters have not been regulated universally in the applicable laws. They are regulated in the ordinances of the presidents of the courts of appeals – separately for each of the 11 jurisdictions of those courts.

Further, according to the initial assumptions, the information portal originally was to be used only for posting less material, informal information on the

¹ The regulation contained in Article 15z(9) of the Covid-19 Act applies both to civil- and criminal proceedings.

² Print of the Polish Sejm of the 9th term, No. 899.

course of a court case. It was only during the Covid-19 epidemic that its functionalities were expanded and it became possible to use it for making available (serving) court letters. After the initial organisational chaos caused by the short *vacatio legis* of only 14 days, as a rule, the new regulations worked well in practice. However, as already mentioned, the regulations providing for the service of letters via the information portal are episodic – they will cease to apply one year following the recall of the state of epidemic threat.

It is commonly held that the service of court letters in the electronic form should be implemented on a permanent basis. What is more, pleadings should be added to the existing regulations. They should be delivered in the electronic form too. The existing practice where each year there are millions of pleadings (frequently thick documents with multiple enclosures) submitted in paper should be discontinued once and for all. Allowing submission of pleadings in the paper form would save time and money, and would help protect the natural environment too.

It would be easy to implement such a solution for professional legal representatives – they would only need to be obliged to submit pleadings in the electronic form. That would allow for delivering documents in the electronic form to the opposite party. It would not require any revolution. Already the absolute majority of attorneys make pleadings in the electronic form. It is only because of the archaic regulations that they need to print them out and submit them in the paper form (along with copies).

It does not, however, seem right yet to impose the duty to submit pleadings in the electronic form on parties acting in person (without professional legal representative). There is still a major group of participants in court proceedings, particularly the elderly and those who live in rural areas, who are digitally excluded. Implementing a universal duty of submitting pleadings in the electronic form would violate the right to court (right to a fair trial) of those people. At most, there could be a regulation stating that parties acting in person may (but are not required to) submit pleadings in the electronic form.

Implementing a duty whereby parties must be represented by professional legal representatives (the so-called mandatory representation by an attorney) at least in the most important cases heard by the regional courts in the first instance, could solve the problem of digital exclusion to some extent. Mandatory representation by an advocate was effective in Poland before World War II and it is postulated that the regulation be restored [4, p. 61]. However, in such a case, guaranteeing the right to court (the right to a fair trial) would require providing a public legal representative (funded by the State) for any person who cannot afford an advocate or an attorney-at-law on his/her own. This solution would be too costly and that is why it has not been implemented. This is one of the reasons why pleadings in Poland are still, as a rule, submitted in the paper form rather than electronically.

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